

ogy, lack of agro-technology, lack of suitable varieties, and weed problems. Among these primary causes, irregular hydrology was most critical as this often resulted in waterlogging or flash floods. The socioeconomic constraints include the low economic status of farmers, their lack of knowledge, and their small landholdings. Economic status was directly influenced by cash on hand, credit facilities, and technical know-how.

Appropriate crops/varieties, better drainage facili-

ties, and improved agro-technology were the solutions recommended to increase the productivity of deepwater areas. Rajshree, Vaidehi, and Barh Avrodhi for medium deep, waterlogged areas (up to 0.5 m water depth); Sudha, Sabita, and Jalpriya for deepwater (0.5–1.0 m); and Varidhi, Jalmagna, and Jalnidhi for very deepwater (>1.0 m) were identified as promising varieties for the DWR ecologies. They have drought and submergence tolerance, and they can grow

long. Suitable varieties for pre-flood crop mixtures and post-flood environments should additionally be identified or introduced to further increase productivity. The performance of drainage facilities can be improved by diverting excess water to canals that would then be used for irrigation purposes or for operating fishponds. Appropriate agro-technology such as rotational rice-fish farming should be promoted.

Farmers' participatory diagnosis of the flood-prone deepwater rice-cropping system in eastern India

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The flood-prone deepwater rice (DWR) areas of eastern India are spread over 3.9 million ha. Here, rice is grown as rainfed dryland or under shallow flooding for the first 1–3 mo and then flooded to depths exceeding 50 cm for a month or longer. About 12% of the rice-growing area of eastern India is under the DWR ecosystem. The main DWR areas are located in eastern Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal, Assam, and Orissa, where productivity is very poor (1 t ha⁻¹). Deepwater areas, called *chaurs* or *tals*, are situated in remote areas and their environment is very complex and unpredictable, often times subjected to stresses of water stagnation. A

farmer participatory evaluation was done at two sites—Biraul chaur (north Bihar) and Suraha tal (eastern Uttar Pradesh)—to identify and develop ecologically sustainable and economically viable technologies that can improve the production potential of DWR farming systems.

Agroecosystem analysis and system diagnosis of farmers' problems were done in 11 villages with 48 farmers. Problems and issues related to DWR ecosystems were prioritized. On the basis of problem ranking and participatory rural appraisal, the common problems encountered in DWR growing environments were waterlogging, flash/intermittent floods, lack of suit-

able varieties/cropping patterns, lack of improved management practices, and socioeconomic/bureaucratic difficulties. Identification of appropriate crop/DWR varieties, sustainable and improved agricultural technologies, suitable cropping/farming systems, and better drainage facilities were the solutions mentioned. Based on the solutions identified, farmers' participatory on-farm and on-station activities were designed and evaluated.

A large number of strains/cultivars/varieties were tested in different DWR growing conditions—0.5 m, 0.5–1.0 m, and > 1.0 m flood-water depth. Nine varieties—Rajshree, Vaidehi, and Barh

Avrodhi for medium deep, waterlogged (up to 0.5 m); Sudha, Sabita, and Jalpriya for deepwater (0.5–1.0 m); and Varidhi, Jalmagna, and Jalnidhi for very deepwater (>1.0 m water depth)—were identified as promising. These varieties gave superior performance in various on-farm trials, with 15–25% higher yield over local varieties (Table 1). Rajshree, Sabita, and Barh Avrodhi had better performance under delayed planting in medium deepwater conditions (Table 2). Sabita and Barh Avrodhi were promising in a double-transplanting situation, whereas Sudha and Sabita fared well under random/haphazard planting. Pusa Baisakhi and NP 28 were found to be suitable mungbean varieties for the pre-flood crop mixture as a DWR intercrop.

Application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ at the onset of the first monsoon and line sowing increased yield by 13%. Improved varieties with improved management practices and need-based plant protection measures gave 30% more yield than the farmers' management practices. Preemergence application of butachlor and 2,4-D at 1.5 and 0.5 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, was effective in reducing weeds in pre-flood environments. Vaidehi and Barh Avrodhi proved to be better weed competitors.

In pre-flood, mixed cropping, on-farm evaluation, average productivity of DWR + *Capsularis* jute crop mixture was 3.19 t ha⁻¹ (rice yield equivalent). This was fol-

lowed by DWR + mungbean (2.44 t ha⁻¹). The DWR + *Capsularis* jute combination gave as high as 4.37 t ha⁻¹ yield equivalent, a substantial gain in this environment. During the postflood environment, *paira* cropping of *Bakala* (*Vicia faba*) registered the highest yield equivalent (3.47 t ha⁻¹), followed by lentil, linseed, and mustard. Among the cropping systems, the highest mean yield equiva-

lent (3.54 t ha⁻¹) was given by DWR-lentil, followed by DWR-wheat and DWR-linseed (Table 3). After DWR harvest, the possibility of cultivating boro (dry-season) rice was assured both in farmers' fields and at research stations, especially in water-stagnant areas. Gautam, Rasi, Pusa 2-21, IR64, Sarjoo 52, Pant 12, and Prabhat were evaluated as promising cultivars for the boro season.

Table 1. Varietal performance in farmers' participatory on-farm evaluation under deepwater rice ecosystems (mean of 3 y).

DWR sub-ecosystem	Farmers participating (no.)	Mean peak water depth (cm)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				
			Barh Avrodhi	Madhukar	Vaidehi	Rajshree	Kariywa local
Medium deepwater	10	34.5–52.0	2.52	2.30	2.59	2.47	2.30
Deepwater	13	74.3–103.3	Jalpriya	Sudha	Chakiya 59	Sabita	Kariywa local
			1.75	1.83	1.60	1.90	1.66
Very deepwater	11	122.7–145.5	Jalmagna	Jalnidhi	Varidhi	–	Jaisurya local
			1.49	1.59	1.69	–	1.58

Table 2. Effect of planting dates and varieties on grain yield (t ha⁻¹) under the flood-prone, medium deepwater rice ecosystem (on-station pooled data of 3 y).

Planting date	Varieties					
	Rajshree	Sabita	Barh Avrodhi	Madhukar	Vaidehi	BKP 246
30 Jul (30-d-old seedlings)	2.40	3.03	2.34	2.15	2.93	3.10
30 Aug (60-d-old seedlings)	1.75	1.78	1.36	1.30	2.10	1.43
30 Aug (30-d-old seedlings)	1.25	1.22	1.76	0.75	0.85	0.90
Difference between						
Date mean at the same level of variety	LSD (P = 0.05)					
Variety mean at the same level of planting date	0.38					
	0.31					

Table 3. Farmers' participatory on-farm evaluation under different flood-prone DWR-based cropping systems (mean of 3 y).

Cropping system	Farmers participating (no.)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a									
		DWR + sesame			DWR + mungbean			DWR + jute fiber			DWR only
		a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c	
Preflood mixed cropping with DWR	5	1.23	0.15	2.14	0.98	0.36	2.44	0.96	1.12	3.19	1.41
Postflood <i>paira</i> cropping with DWR	5	DWR-bakala			DWR-lentil			DWR-linseed			DWR-mustard
		1.54	0.55	3.47	1.56	0.25	2.56	1.53	0.18	2.43	a b c
DWR cropping system	5	DWR-wheat			DWR-lentil			DWR-linseed			
		1.51	1.21	3.39	1.45	0.52	3.54	1.5	0.34	3.20	
DWR-boro rice	6	DWR-boro (Sarjoo 52)			DWR-boro (Gautam)			DWR-boro (IR64)			DWR-boro (Pant 12)
		1.20	6.80	9.70	1.38	6.85	9.94	1.12	7.15	10.0	1.50 6.50 9.60

^aa = DWR, b = mixed crop/second crop, c = yield equivalent in terms of DWR at prevailing market prices.

Postharvest technology of rice: role of farm women in storing grains

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The importance of grain storage in rice production is often ignored. Inadequate storage facilities and improper storage methods can cause considerable losses to rice farmers. Total postharvest losses in food grain account for 9.3% of total production, 6.5% of which are losses incurred during storage alone (Gandhi 1983). Minimizing these losses can increase food grain supply, thereby making headway in feeding millions of hungry people. Farmers must therefore learn how to store rice properly, especially during the transitory period, to protect the grains from the effects of weather or from insects and pests.

Women's role in this respect is yet to be recognized, in spite of their significant in-

volvement in food processing and food storage. Women farmers play distinct and well-accepted roles in all the activities of rice cultivation, and 93% of the farm women are themselves actively involved in storing rice grains (Sumathi and Budhar 2003). They receive less than 5% of extension services worldwide, their priorities are rarely reflected in agricultural research or national policies, and their role as agricultural producers is still largely unrecognized and has not been addressed (LEISA 2002).

We conducted a study among women farmers to find out the role of farm women in grain storage using different storage practices. We also aimed to identify the needs of farm women with

respect to effective storage of grains. Data were collected at Tirupattur taluk of Vellore District in Tamil Nadu, India. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood of the people in this area and rice is grown on about 72,000 ha in three distinct seasons. A sample of 100 women farmers was selected randomly from five villages (20 from each village). Most of them cultivate small farms (0.1–1 ha) and some who have more land (>1 ha) live in clusters. Through a well-structured interview schedule, data on the adoption of different storage methods and feedback regarding problems in adoption were collected.

Among 12 storage practices identified, four (see Table 1)—drying grains before storage, stacking bags